

METHODOLOGICAL PRINCIPLE OF PERSONALITY PSYCHOLOGY

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Abstract. This study highlights the problems of personality psychology and their analytical theoretical foundations. It discusses the stages of personality development, identity, socialization of the personality and its assumptions, the interpretation of the personality problem in psychology.

Understanding the method of personality psychology depends on understanding the subject of general psychology and sociology.

Keywords: phenomenology of personality, individuality, philosophy, needs, emotion, sociology, object, dynamic psychology, subject.

SHAXS PSIXOLOGIYASINING METODOLOGIK PRINTSIPI

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqotda shaxs psixologiyasi muammolari va ularning tahlilii nazariy asoslari yoritib berilgan. Unda shaxsning rivojlanish bosqichlari, o'ziga xosligi, shaxsning ijtimoiylashuvi va uning ustanovklari, psixologiyada shaxs muammosi talqini shaxs psixologiyasi metodini tushunishning umumiy psixologiya va sotsiologiya predmetini tushunishga bog'liqligi keltirib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: shaxs fenomenologiyasi, individuallik, falsafa, ehtiyojlar, his-tuyg'ular, sotsiologiya, ob'ekt, dinamik psixologiya, sub'ekt.

МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ ПРИНЦИП ПСИХОЛОГИИ ЛИЧНОСТИ

Аннотация. В настоящем исследовании освещаются проблемы психологии личности и их аналитические теоретические основы. В нем рассматриваются этапы развития личности, идентичности, социализации индивида и ее предпосылки, а также интерпретация проблем личности в психологии. Понимание метода психологии личности зависит от понимания предмета общей психологии и социологии.

Ключевые слова: феноменология личности, индивидуальность, философия, потребность, эмоция, социология, объект, динамическая психология, субъект..

Introduction

The definition of the subject area of personality psychology is associated with the solution of a number of significant issues. In modern psychological literature (see, for example, Asmolov A.G., 1990), three most important features of the cognitive situation of personality study are distinguished:

- the richness of the phenomenology of personality, expressed in the diversity of individual human characteristics (attitudes, traits, needs, emotions, preferences, etc.), which we correlate with the studied area of knowledge;

- the interdisciplinary status of the personality problem, which means that this concept describes a very broad area of knowledge, individual aspects of which are studied not only by psychology, but also by philosophy, history, sociology and other sciences;
- the ambiguity of the position that the personality occupies in the course of research: it can be (alternately or simultaneously) both the object and the subject of research.

The first feature - the richness of the phenomenology of personality - is reflected in two different points of view. According to one of them, the entire diversity of personality manifestations can be reduced to some one mental phenomenon (temperament type, behavior style, motivation, speech tempo and speed, etc.), the precise and adequate study of which would allow us to study the personality as a whole. According to another point of view, a person as a personality is a systemic object interacting with other complex systems (nature, society). The need for a systemic approach arises precisely when the diversity of information obtained about a given phenomenon requires generalization and systematization, when, in order to create a holistic picture, not only the properties immanent to the object are studied, but also such features that manifest themselves in the process of interaction with other systemic objects. The famous German psychologist, the author of field theory, Kurt Lewin said that the study of personality outside of its environment, outside of context will lead to the exclusion from the analysis of properties important for understanding the essence of man, which is why "instead of isolating from the situation this or that isolated element, the significance of which cannot be assessed without considering the situation as a whole, field theory, as a rule, prefers to start with the characteristics of the situation as a whole" and only after that "the various aspects and parts of the situation are subjected to more and more specific and detailed analysis" (Lewin K., 2001. "Dynamic Psychology", p. 253).

Thus, considering any phenomenon as a system, we must study it in different plans:

- 1) as a certain qualitative unit, a system with its own specific, unique features;
- 2) as part of a macrostructure (for example, society);
- 3) as part of microsystems, the laws of which it obeys.

In his general theoretical and methodological work, B. F. Lomov wrote the following: "... mental phenomena are formed, developed and manifested in the processes of activity and communication. But they do not belong to activity or communication, but to their subject - a social individual - a personality. Thus, both the problem of activity and the problem of communication "close" on the problem of personality". Consequently, the phenomenology and patterns of communication, its psychological component and other aspects of it (communication) that are connected with it must be studied from the position of personal conditioning, from the position of considering the personality as a subject of communication, realizing in this specific type of activity functions significant for the personality and oriented towards achieving goals significant for the personality. It should be taken into account that deep motivation or very general motivating reasons may not be reflected upon by the personality. Being not obvious, these motivating reasons may not be reflected upon in scientific research that is not specifically oriented towards their identification. Communication as a specific type of personality activity is directed, on the one hand, by tasks determined by the external situation and more general goals realized by the subject of labor and other activities. On the other hand, communication as a type of personality activity is directed and regulated by personal processuality, its incessant being with its internal tasks.

That is, a person often enters into communication in order to receive support, objectifying his subjective ideas in relations with the Other, or, on the contrary, avoids relations if he feels their possible destructiveness for his subjective world. The nature of relations between the internal and the external and, accordingly, the question of determination of personality activity by external and internal causes is complex and does not have a clear answer. S. L. Rubinstein wrote that with the appearance of man, a special, mutual implication of being and man arises.

In our society, the description given to a person is determined by his attitude to the process of building a developed society and his real participation in this process. Changes in a person's mental state depend on the external environment and social upbringing. Relatively stable and relatively variable characteristics of a person form a complex unity, that is, a dynamic structure, consisting of the unity and interdependence of personal qualities. The psychological study of a person includes the solution of two main scientific problems: 1. Determining the individual structure that distinguishes each person from other people. This makes it possible to predict behavior. 2. It requires distinguishing several parts of the structure of a person's personality. The sum of these parts forms a human personality. Currently, in foreign psychology, a theory that distinguishes two main parts in the human personality, formed by the influence of two factors, namely biological and social factors, occupies a prominent place. It was proposed that the human personality is divided into "Endopsychic" (internal) and "Exopsychic" (external) parts. The "endopsychic" with a natural basis depends on biological conditions, while the "exopsychic" depends on social factors. The error of the two-factor theory is that this theory mechanically opposes the social factor to the biological factor, the environment to the biological structure, and the "exopsychic" to the "endopsychic". However, there are other options for approaching the issue of natural and social factors affecting the composition and structure of the personality. For example, such a study was conducted: the study revealed that the structure of the personality of people whose height does not exceed 80 - 130 cm. was largely similar. It is possible to see childlike simplicity, high resilience, and the absence of shame in them. A person actively interacts with the world around him through his activities. The activity of a person is understood as the impact that a person has on the surrounding external environment. Not only people, but also animals interact with the external environment.

Conclusion

The science and practice of contemporary psychology recognize that it is difficult to study individual activity in isolation from the social sphere. Emphasizing the provision of information about personality psychology, it is necessary to pay more attention to the study of socially existing laws of personality development.

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